

Strategizing Faster and Wholesome Implementation of NEP-2020 the Way Forward for Transforming India into a Knowledge Superpower

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Prof. Aithal stated that already many Universities have started implementing NEP and the Srinivas University has introduced the NEP based curriculum in 2021-22 as a challenging academic endeavour. He mentioned that the process of introducing NEP from the top instead from the bottom as a means to reverse the process for better result. Humanities and Social Sciences have prioritised to engulf NEP matrix before Engineering programmes have gone for such transformation. He insisted at NEP policies need to be utilised to improve the quality of life in the society before it becomes obsolete and irrelevant. He highlighted one of the objectives of NEP -2020 is to provide high-quality, low-cost education to everyone with an expectation of holistic & research-oriented progress. There is an urge to formulize strategies by involving technology in implementing NEP at school and university levels. He stated that transformation in Indian HE could be conceived by indianising the educational system by internalizing it by wording out 'zero' as 'zero' replacing the westernized 'o'. The methodology adopted would call on the transformation from the teacher centered learning into student-centric class-room learning which involves the following paradigm shifts

From Traditional Classroom to Experiential learning

From Subject oriented to Industry oriented

From Knowledge driven to Skill driven and new knowledge creation

From Theory based syllabus to Project based Syllabus

From Lesson driven to Research driven

- From Mono-disciplinary to Multi-disciplinary
- From STEM to STEAM (Art, culture & design), STEAM is the crux of NEP
- From Memorization based evaluation to Competency based evaluation
- From Degree Completion focus to Employability & Entrepreneur ability focus
- From Campus Based to Ubiquitous
- From Monopoly Closed System to Competitive Open System

The objective of higher education is to enhance the confidence by identifying problems and making productive participation in solving them which would ensure comfortable life for all. The challenges ahead are in creating and nurturing innovators not wealth creators. The quality of life may be improved by getting the basic needs for living, attaining the comfortable life style, fulfilling all the desires through maximum utilization of indianised technology 4.0 seems to be the ideal resolution to optimize the use of time and other resources.

The highlights of NEP are to enrich the school system with 15 years of enhanced learning which is subdivided into 5 (Foundation) + 3 (Preparatory) + 3 (Middle S) + 4 (Secondary S) which leads to holistic education by creating strong foundation grounded on super- specialization, while college education is structured as 4 (UG) + 1 (PG) + 3/4 (R) focusing on Multi-disciplinary and Super-specialty (5 to 8 years) domains of learning by incorporating Student Centric Flexible ABC through Digital University. To increase the GER percentage, it strategically requires the formulation of Higher Education Commission of India to bring out the expected changes from the bottom to the top. When it comes to the future of

NEP, it is integral that it would undergo changes along with technological forecasting and predictions for upgrading to meet future changes. Prof. Aithal categorised the future into different stages reflecting the expected changes in the educational system as Gen Z till 2028, Gen A till 2035, Gen B till 2050, and the fourth stage which would evolve into extreme levels of changes and consumptions like artificial food, artificial water, fusion based renewable energy, health for everyone with organ regeneration and anti-aging technologies, life-span expansion, technology singularity stage, self-assembling buildings, automated homes, pico-technology, space elevators, decarbonized electricity, super/hyper intelligent machines, and finally Super Intelligent Humans.

He concluded with the remark that the future supported by technology would possibly connect brain with brain or brain with computers reaching for creating ubiquitous existence, omni-potent renewable power sources, omni-science comprising infinite borderless knowledge and immortal life-span expansion utilizing Bio-nanotechnology.

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